

**Assessing the Practice of Non-pharmaceutical Interventions for the Prevention of COVID-19 among Civil Servants in Rivers State
BRIGGS NCT.**

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Background: Covid-19 is a severe acute respiratory syndrome caused by the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. It was first discovered in a 55-year-old male in China in 2019, hence the term “Covid-19”. Non-Pharmaceutical Interventions (NPI) are effective public health measures for the prevention and control of Covid-19 pandemic. Some of these interventions include the wearing of face masks, hand washing, use of alcohol-based hand sanitizers, and physical/social distancing.

The Rivers State Government has emphasized the use of these measures in the work environment in all Ministries, Departments, and Agencies.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from March, 2021 to April, 2021 among the Directorate cadre (Grade levels 14 to 16) of the Civil Service. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 380 Civil Servants. A semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaire was used for data collection. Data analysis was with SPSS version 20. A p-value of 0.05 or less is considered as statistically significant.

Results: 65% of the respondents were males while 35% were females with mean age of 48.6 +/- 4.2 (males) and 45.4 +/- 3.7 (females). 90.3% used face masks alone; 57.8% used hand sanitizers alone, 2.3% observed physical/social distancing alone and 0.8% practiced hand washing alone. Only 17.9% used all the four (4) interventions.

None of these practices were statistically significant.

Table 1. Practice of Non-Pharmaceutical Interventions

Non-Pharmaceutical Interventions	Number	Percentage
Facemasks	343	90.3
Hand Sanitizers	220	57.8
Hand Washing	3	0.8
Physical/Social distancing	9	2.3
Used all four interventions	68	17.9

Discussion: Non-Pharmaceutical interventions were put in place during the first wave of the Covid-19 Pandemic to reduce the spread of the Corona-Virus.

The Non-Pharmaceutical interventions are effective when used in combinations.

To ensure compliance, the Rivers State Government at various times directed Civil Servants on Grade Levels 1 to 10 to work from home in 2020, and Grade Levels 01-13 in early 2021.

Only a few Civil Servants in the Directorate cadre as shown in the study (17.9%), did comply with all the four interventions. It is important that civil servants are continuously enlightened on behavioural changes to ensure strict compliance now that the Delta Variant of the Covid-19 infection is in the country.

Heads of Ministries, Departments and Agencies should ensure that some of the non-pharmaceutical interventions like hand washing points, physical distancing are provided and practiced.

Conclusion: The use of Non-Pharmaceutical Interventions among Civil Servants in Rivers State is not encouraging. Strict monitoring of the Civil Servants in the work environment by the Heads of Ministries, Departments and Agencies is recommended for good compliance.

Key words: Covid-19, Non-Pharmaceutical Interventions, Civil Servants, Rivers State.

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